

Parents' Perceptions about the Role of Hearing in the Development of Language and Speech in Children

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this research was to understand the perceptions of parents on the difficulties of children in language development and speech when they also have hearing impairments. The research focused on three cities in Kosovo, Gjilan, Prishtina and Prizren. Respondents of this research are 60 parents of children with hearing impairments, of the mentioned high schools. The questionnaire measured the opinions of parents regarding the topic we have for research, primary schools in the municipalities of Gjilan, Prishtina and Prizren that are participants in this research. This questionnaire included 29 questions. In conclusion, it is understood that the lower the level of hearing in children, the lower is the development of language and speech in children, $p < 0.01$, $r = -0.531$ **.

KEYWORDS: Perceptions, Hearing Impairment, Language And Speech

I. INTRODUCTION

In everyday life we encounter a large number of children who do not have sufficiently developed language and speech, and the causes of underdevelopment of language and speech in these children are different, where one of these causes may be even hearing loss to the child.

Language is a complex and dynamic system of conventional symbols that is used in various modes for thought and communication. Contemporary views of human language hold that: language evolves within specific historical, social, and cultural contexts; language, as rule-governed behavior, is described by at least five parameters—phonologic, morphologic, syntactic, semantic, and pragmatic; language learning and use are determined by the interaction of biological, cognitive, psychosocial, and environmental factors; effective use of language for communication requires a broad understanding of human interaction including such associated factors as nonverbal cues, motivation, and sociocultural roles. A speech disorder is an impairment of the articulation of speech sounds, fluency and/or voice. A hearing disorder is the result of impaired auditory sensitivity of the physiological auditory system. A hearing disorder may limit the development, comprehension, production, and/or maintenance of speech and/or language. Hearing disorders are classified according to difficulties in detection, recognition, discrimination, comprehension, and perception of auditory information. Individuals with hearing impairment may be described as deaf or hard of hearing (ASHA, 1982).

Carvalho & Carvalho (2009) emphasize that hearing is maintained as a very important biological factor, which plays an essential role in language acquisition and development, and thus hearing loss can cause delays in the development of children, in terms of the field of communication.

It is worth noting that the development of communication skills is essential in early childhood. Thus, poor communication skills at the end of preschool have a negative effect on social, academic, and later work success (Tomblin et al., 2008; Catts et al., 2002).

Language is a social tool used for social interactions, for the purpose of communication. Thus language difficulties have to do with changes in expression development, information retrieval and verbal writing. Thus, early identification of changes in the normal development of the child avoids adverse, later educational effects (Shirmer et al., 2004).

Moret et al., (2007) emphasize that the use of hearing aids has favored in minimizing hearing impairments, in the process of acquisition and development of language in children.

Oliveira et al., (2015) showed that language development is related to the development of listening skills. Hearing impairment results in loss of language development and the greater the rate of hearing loss, the greater the difficulty of perceiving and discriminating speech and language deficits.

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II. METHODOLOGY

A. Participants

The research focused on three cities in Kosovo, Gjilan, Prishtina and Prizren. The selection of schools was done deliberately. Taking into account the fact that the respondents of the research are the parents of children with hearing impairments, then those schools that have students with this problem were selected.

The selected schools in Gjilan are: "Rexhep Elmazi"; Thimi Mitko; " Abaz Ajeti "; " Selami Hallaqi ". In Prishtina: "Elena Gjika", and in Prizren: "Mother Teresa" Resource Center.

Respondents of this research are 60 parents of children with hearing impairments, of the mentioned high schools. Even the selection of parents is done deliberately.

B. Instrument

During this research, the technique of questioning with parents was used, respectively we taked the opinions of the subjects regarding the hearing problems, as causes in the speech difficulties.

The questionnaire has measure the opinions of parents regarding the topic we had for research, the primary schools of the municipalities of Gjilan, Prishtina and Prizren that are participants in this research. The questionnaire had 29 questions.

So the questionnaire used for this research was: "The Speech Questionnaire: an Assessment of Functional Language Ability. International Rehabilitation Medicine (Lincoln, 1982).

C. Procedures

First we got permission from the school principals and then based on the sampling we conducted the conversation or notification of the respondents about the problem, and then the questionnaires were distributed to the parents. Which were distributed three days in a row, on 10.06.2018, 11.06.2018 and 12.06.2018 in all three municipalities at 10 AM.

The data were analyzed with the Statistical Package of Social Sciences - SPSS, and frequency analysis, correlation, t-test, reliability and regression were used.

At the beginning, the school principals were informed about the purpose of the research, then the teachers, parents and students were informed that everything about this research is confidential, so their names will not be misused. The rights of respondents are protected at all costs, and those who refuse to participate in completing the questionnaire are free not to complete it.

III. RESULTS

Based on the frequency analysis we understand the parents' answers on the questionnaire variables.

About the question: "Does the child respond appropriately to familiar phrases?", 50% of parents answer never, 25% of them answer rarely, 22% often and 3% always.

Also for the other variable: "The child expresses ordinary words appropriately", 35% of parents answer never, 57% rarely and 8% more often.

About the question: "Does the child understand the simple instructions given by you using gestures?", 37% of parents answer with never, 30% answer rarely, 25% more often and 8% with always .

About the question: "Does he / she understand conversations with you about everyday topics?", 33% of parents emphasize never, 60% less often and 7% more often.

Also about the other question: "Does he / she understand the idea or even complicated explanations?", 23% of parents answer never, 67% rarely and 10% more often.

Frequency analysis on the questionnaire variables	Never	Rare	Often	Always
1. "Does the child respond appropriately to familiar phrases?"	50%	25%	22%	3%
2. "The child expresses ordinary words in a very appropriate way"	35%	57%	8%	0%
3. "Does the child understand the simple instructions given by you using gestures?"	37%	30%	25%	8%
4. "Does he/she understand conversations with you about everyday topics?"	33%	0%	60%	7%
5. "Does he/she understand the idea or even complicated explanations?"	23%	67%	0%	10%

Correlation analysis shows that there is a significant positive correlation between the variables: "degree of hearing impairment" and the "current age of the child" $p < 0.01$, $r = .492^{**}$; "degree of hearing impairment" and "the age when hearing difficulty was discovered" $p < 0.01$, $r = .371^{**}$; "adapting the child to the conversation" and his "current age" $p < 0.01$, $r = .362^{**}$; "comprehensibility of instructions" and "current age of the child" $p < 0.01$, $r = .396^{**}$.

Significant negative correlation exists between the variables: "degree of hearing impairment" and "words used by the child" $p < 0.01$, $r = -.531^{**}$.

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Correlation analysis based on questionnaire variables	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Current Age	1					
2. The age when hearing difficulty was discovered	,492**	1				
3. Degree of hearing impairment	,751	,371**	1			
4. Words used by the child	-,122	-,354**	-,531**	1		
5. Adapting the child to the conversation	,362**	,315*	-,353*	,151	1	
6. Comprehensibility of instructions	,396**	,160	,126	,122	,536**	1

CONCLUSIONS

From the research findings we understand that a large proportion of children who have hearing impairments do not respond appropriately to conversations with phrases in the family. We also understand that most children with hearing impairments rarely expresses ordinary words appropriately. Also we understand that most of these children never understand, or rarely understand, the instructions given to them by their parents using gestures as well. Parents also point out that children often try to talk to them about everyday topics. However, they rarely understand the complicated instructions that were given to them.

Also, based on the correlation analysis, we understand that the older the children, the higher the hearing loss. We also understand that the higher the age when hearing difficulty is understood, the higher that difficulty was. The higher the age of the children, the higher the adaptation of the children in the conversation, and at the same time it is worth mentioning that the lower the hearing in children, the lower the development of language and speech in children.

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